

Investigating Lassa Fever Awareness and its Impact on Attitudinal Behavior Among Edo State Residents: A Case Study of the Edo North Senatorial District.

Godwin Aipoh*

Peter Ohimai†

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Abstract

Lassa Fever, a viral hemorrhagic illness endemic to Nigeria and other sub-Saharan African countries, has posed significant public health challenges for decades. This study, conducted in the Edo North Senatorial District, explores the relationship between Lassa Fever awareness and attitudinal behavior among residents. Data was collected through questionnaires distributed across six local government areas, with a sample size of 500 respondents. Analysis using Chi-square tests in SPSS 20.0 revealed that factors such as religion, gender, and local government of residence influence Lassa Fever awareness levels. The findings emphasize the importance of promoting awareness about Lassa Fever, highlighting the need for targeted educational campaigns. This research provides valuable insights for policymakers and organizations seeking to address misconceptions about Lassa Fever and improve public health awareness in Nigeria.

*Department of Statistics, AP (E-mail: goodgoddy789@gmail.com)

†Department of Statistics, AP (Email: ohipetderock10@gmail.com)

1 Introduction

Lassa Fever, a viral hemorrhagic illness, poses a significant threat to public health, especially in Nigeria, where awareness levels are low and misconceptions about this deadly disease abound. Developing economies are the most affected during national or global disease outbreaks, primarily due to inadequate infrastructure and poor execution of successive strategies. This paper focuses on a distinct location in South-South Nigeria and the locality in Edo State is made up of 6 local government areas. Afenmai¹ is a group of people living in the northern part of Edo State's South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria. Afenmai or Afemai people occupy six local government areas in Edo state: Etsako West, Etsako Central, Etsako East, Owan East, Owan West, and Akoko Edo. These make up the Edo-North Senatorial District. Since 1969, there have been incidents of Lassa fever in the district.

Lassa Fever is a disease endemic in West Africa, including Nigeria. The earliest record of the disease was in the 1950s but the virus was isolated by the Centre for Disease Control (CDC), Atlanta, USA, in 1969 (Frame et al., 1970; McCormick et al., 1987; Carey et al., 1972). Since its discovery in 1969 in the village of Lassa in Borno State, Nigeria, there have been countless outbreaks of various magnitude and severity across West Africa. Estimates of annual incidences of Lassa Fever across this region reached as high as 300,000 infections and 5,000 deaths (CDC 2006). However, many cases remain unaccounted for due to scarce resources to diagnose the illness and inadequate surveillance. Consequently, the virus is transmitted to humans through cuts, scratches or inhaled (Adebiyi, 2012).

Early signs include fever, headache, and general malaise, followed by a sore throat, nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, and diarrhea in some cases. After 4 to 7 days, many patients will start to feel better, but a small minority will proceed to display symptoms such as edema, hypertension, bleeding, and shock. Death from Lassa fever most commonly occurs 10 to 14 days after symptom onset, (Ehichioya et al., 2010). Because of its high case fatality rate, ability to spread easily by human-to-human contact, and potential for aerosol release, Lassa virus is classified as a Biosafety Level 4 (BSL4) and NIAID Biodefense category A agent. Moreover, the impact of the disease in endemic regions of West Africa is immense, and therefore, means to diagnose, treat, and prevent this viral hemorrhagic fever will provide a significant public health benefit.

As at the time of this study, the authors are not aware of a vaccine for Lassa Fever, and the only available drug, Ribavirin, is only effective if administered early in infection (within the first 6 days after disease onset). One of the hallmarks of Lassa virus infection is the apparent absence of functional antibodies during acute infection. A fundamental understanding of the mechanisms of antibody-mediated neutralization of Lassa virus may have significant implications for the generation of antibody-based therapeutics or epitope-targeted vaccines, (Ogbu et al., 2007; Grant et al., 2014).

The study aimed to answer the following research questions and hypothesis: Does the awareness depend on the attitudinal behavior of Lassa Fever? Does awareness depend on social status? Does Lassa Fever awareness depend on the Local Government of residents? Does Lassa Fever awareness depend on Religion? The authors constructed four(4) hypotheses that the study targeted to provide empirical evidence. $H0_1$: Lassa fever awareness is independent of religion. $H0_2$: Lassa fever awareness is independent of gender. $H0_3$: Lassa fever awareness is independent of the

¹also spelled as Afemia

local government of residents. H_{04} : Attitudinal behavior is independent of awareness of Lassa fever.

Definition of Terms:

2 Literature Review

For the past three decades, Nigeria and many sub-Saharan Africa have been under the canopy of epidemics that shed them from rapid development. Many citizens in most of these countries have been ravaged by diseases such as measles, whooping cough, malaria, yellow fever, typhoid fever, HIV/AIDS, Lassa fever, polio, etc. The prevalence of some of these endemic diseases has attracted the attention of the World Health Organization (WHO), its specialized agencies, and research scientists.

Historically, it started at Lassa village near Maiduguri, Borno State (1969), that same outbreak had a nosocomial spread to Jos, Plateau State (1969-1970). Thereafter, Lassa fever outbreaks occurred in Zonkwa, Kaduna State and Onitsha, Anambra State (1974), Pankshin, Plateau State (1976), Ekpoma, Aboh-Mbaise, and Aba (1989), Ekpoma (endemic for Lassa) (1989 till date), Lafia (December 1993 to February 1994) Northern part of Edo State, including Auchi, Igarra, and Ibilo (2001 and 2004), Ebonyi and Ogun States (2005) Edo, Plateau, Kogi, Benue, Ondo, Nasarawa, Ebonyi (2007/2008), Edo, Nasarawa, Gombe, Kaduna, Plateau, Ondo, Lagos States and FCT (2009), Kaduna, Kebbi, Plateau, Taraba, Edo, Kogi, Ondo (2010).

Several programs have been put in place among African nations to reduce and eradicate the havoc these diseases have caused humans. Among these are Operation Roll Back Malaria, Expanded Programme on Immunization (EPI), and free treatment to people with whooping cough, HIV/AIDS, and Leprosy in addition to free distribution of treated mosquito nets to millions of people. In Nigeria, apart from setting up the Presidential Council on AIDS (PCA), HIV Emergency Action Plan (HEAP), and National AIDS and STD Control Programme (NASCP) in response to the scourge, the government has also set up a three-tier committee. At the national level, the National Action Committee on HIV/AIDS (NACA), State Action Committee (SACA), and the Local Government Action Committee (LACA) was established to respectively coordinate and address the problem of HIV/AIDS at the federal, state and local government levels [Falaye \(2004\)](#). Also media publicity on the dangers of mosquitoes as a vector of malaria fever in the tropics was carried out to sensitize Nigerians immediately after the summit on Operation RollBack Malaria was held in Abuja in the year 2000, Although no conscious effort by the various health ministries to carry out the message to the grassroots, who were the most vulnerable of the population to the scourge of malaria, ([Falaye, 2004](#)). This was followed by free distribution of treated mosquito nets to millions of Households. In the same vein, immunization against polio was fervently pursued. Little or no awareness has been created among people about Lassa fever, which is equally endemic in many parts of Nigeria. Lassa fever an, endemic acute viral hemorrhagic disease, was first discovered in Sierra Leone in the 1950s, but the virus responsible for the infection was not known until 1969, when it claimed the lives of two missionary nurses. This fever was named after a village called Lassa in Borno State, Nigeria. Subsequent outbreaks of the disease were recorded in Liberia and Sierra Leone. Lassa fever cases have equally been reported in the United States of America. It has claimed many lives, not only in Nigeria but in other parts of West Africa.

Health records have indicated that many have lost their lives to the infection oblivious of it

(Adebiyi, 2012) (Oyetimi, 2012). As noted by Ehichioya et al. (2010), 3 disease-endemic zones exist within Nigeria: the north-eastern region around Lafia, the central region around Jos, and the southern region around Onitsha. The outbreak of Lassa fever was widely noticed around these regions. Between 2005 and 2008, the epidemic was witnessed in some states like Kano, Nassarawa, Plateau, Ogun, and other towns like Onitsha in Enugu State, Aboh-Mbaise, and Owerri in Imo State, and Ekpoma in Edo State. The Federal Capital Territory was not left out as nine cases were reported, with two infected persons dying.

Furthermore, in 2010, this deadly disease claimed over seventeen (17) lives in Kebbi State, and 22 lives in Irrua Specialist Hospital, Edo State between January 2011 and February 2012 (Akpede, 2012). A man was also confirmed dead of Lassa Fever on August 30th, 2012 in Oyo State (Ogbu et al., 2007) (Oguntola, 2012). Its outbreak was also reported in Markurdi, Benue State in January 2013 (Abdulraheem, 2002; Adefisan, 2014). This disease not only claimed the lives of infected people, four (4) doctors at the National Hospital, Abuja, two (2) doctors at Ebonyi State University Teaching Hospital (EBSUTH) and a medical personnel at the University of Benin Teaching Hospital (UBTH) were said to have died due to lack of proper infection control. This shows that its outbreak has spread to all geo-political regions of Nigeria. The situation of Lassa fever in Nigeria is captured by Ibekwe (2012) while presenting the report of Pest Control Association of Nigeria, (PECAN) lamented that no fewer than 3,000 Nigerians die annually from Lassa fever. These statistics are quite alarming when compared with the report of WHO (2012) that between 300,000 to 500,000 cases of Lassa fever and 5,000 deaths occur yearly across the West African sub-region.

According to WHO, in fatal cases, death usually takes place within 14 days of onset. It further argued that the disease is especially severe late in pregnancy, which would invariably lead to foetal or maternal death in over 80 percent of cases in the third trimester. This further supported the earlier findings of Ehichioya et al. (2010) on the characteristics of Lassa fever in Nigeria. The mastomys rat which lives in and around many homes in Africa has been identified as the carrier of the virus. Medical experts according to Adebiyi (2012); Ogunyedeka (2012), indicate that contracting the fever usually occurs through coming in contact with the multi-mammate rat's excreta or urine. The virus is usually contained in the urine and droppings of the mastomys rodents. Humans can easily get infected when these rats make droppings or urinate on foods that are meant to be consumed. Coming in direct contact with these droppings can also lead to infection. Touching open sores or cuts could lead to its transmission. Since these rodents can be found around homes, they usually scavenge on human food wastes or poorly stored food.

The infection could be airborne when sweeping the droppings of these rodents; the particles of such droppings could be inhaled thereby leading to infection (?). Lassa fever is not gender or sex-specific as it occurs both in men and women. Individuals who stand at greater risk are those who live in overcrowded environments, slums, and rural areas where sanitation is not only poor but is lacking. The rodents that carry the Lassa virus largely thrive in such places. It is the common practice of many farmers in rural areas in Nigeria to spread their farm products, especially pepper, melon, maize, and tubers meant to be processed into flour along the road sideways to dry. This practice easily encourages the contamination of the foodstuff by the virus-carrying rodents which come out of a nearby bush to feed on them thereby aiding transmission.

The Federal Government and the various State Governments have embarked on sensitization of residents of the states on the preventive and proactive measures to be taken against the outbreak of the fever. Knowing the awareness among rural people that rats/rodents are vectors of Lassa

fever should be the first step in the fight against Lassa fever. While Lassa fever is mild or has no observable symptoms in about 80 percent of people infected with the virus, the remaining 20 percent have a severe multi-system disease. Approximately 15-20 percent of patients hospitalized for Lassa fever will die and this could cause panic with serious socio-economic consequences. The death rates are particularly high for pregnant women and their unborn babies. About one-third of those who survive may have mild to severe degrees of deafness, and in many cases the hearing loss is permanent. During epidemics, the Lassa fever case-fatality rate may reach 50 percent.

Having consider many research works, the researcher find out that most of the study carry out by researchers did not centred on the altitudinal behaviour as related to the awareness of Lassa fever. That is why the researcher embarked on the study of Lassa fever Awareness On The Attitude Behavior among Nigeria using Edo North as a case study².

3 Data Source and Methodology

In this work certain methods were used, this chapter explains in detail the procedure adopted in arriving at the inference of this research work. Research decision is the framework of investigating a research problem in other words it refers to the methods used in collecting data that is to be used in investigating and analyzing a research problem. Primary data is used in this research work.

The research method adopted for the present study was a primary source using questionnaires to collect the data across the six local government areas of Edo North senatorial district. The population of the study is 500 questionnaires. This is because Edo North comprises six local government areas, namely Akoko Edo, Estako Central, Estako East, Estako West, Owan East, and Owan West, making up the population of the study. Simple random sampling was used to select the sample from the population in Edo North, which consists of these six local government areas.

The authors designed a structured questionnaire to collect data across the 6 (six) local Governments of Edo North. This instrument was subject to ACCRU.³ The instrument was validated by Dr. F.I. Ogege⁴, Mr. Shaib Ismail Omade⁵, and Mr. Anthony Ohimai.⁶, all are faculty members at the renowned Auchi Polytechnic. The authors distributed six hundred (600) questionnaires, with each local government receiving 100 questionnaires. Upon collection, the questionnaires underwent content, criterion, and construct validity checks (Evans et al., 1985; Krosnick, 1999; Ong, 2012), resulting in 449 questionnaires meeting our standards.

For data analysis, the study utilized the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS 20) for both descriptive and inferential analyses. For the inferential analysis, Chi-square was employed to ascertain if a systematic relationship exists between two variables. In this scenario, the test aimed to determine the significant difference between the observed frequencies, and the expected or theoretical frequencies (i.e., the goodness of fit tests), denoted as χ^2 . The Chi-square value is obtained from the formula:

²For further details on Symptoms, treatment, and prevention of Lassa fever, professional medical personnel should be contacted or the updated guidelines as provided by WHO.

³ACCRU stands for A-accurate; C-complete; C-consistent; R-reliable, and U-uniform

⁴A seasoned faculty member with over 20 years of experience

⁵A distinguished researcher and faculty member in the Department of Statistics

⁶A faculty member and scientist in the Department of Science Laboratory Technology

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{j=1}^J \frac{(O_{ij} - E_{ij})^2}{E_{ij}} \quad (1)$$

$$\chi^2 = \chi^2 \alpha (r - 1)(c - 1) \quad (2)$$

where O_{ij} = observed frequencies in the i th cell, E_{ij} = expected frequencies in the j th cell, and $(r - 1)(c - 1)$ is the degree of freedom for a two-way classification. In drawing our conclusion, we compare Equation (1) to Equation (2), where the former is referred to as the calculated chi-square and the latter is tabulated. Our decision rule is thus:

If χ^2 calculated $<$ χ^2 tabulated, accept H_0

If χ^2 calculated $>$ χ^2 tabulated, accept H_1

4 Data Presentation, Analysis, and Discussion

4.1 Data Presentation

Table 1: Age Distribution of Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
17-24	223	49.7	49.7	49.7
25-32	124	27.6	27.6	77.3
33-40	28	6.2	6.2	83.5
41-48	30	6.7	6.7	90.2
49-56	15	3.3	3.3	93.5
57+	29	6.5	6.5	100.0
Total	449	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2016

Table 2: Religion Distribution

Religion	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Christianity	351	78.2	78.2	78.2
Muslim	80	17.8	17.8	96.0
Others	18	4.0	4.0	100.0
Total	449	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2016

From Table 1, 223 of the respondents, amounting to 49.7 percent, are between the ages of 17 to 24 years. Additionally, 125 respondents, accounting for 27.6 percent, fall within the age range of 25 to 32 years. Furthermore, 28 respondents, constituting 6.2 percent, are between the ages of 30 to 40 years. Moreover, 30 respondents, making up 6.7 percent, are aged between 41 to 48 years. Additionally, 15 respondents, comprising 3.3 percent, are within the age range of 49 to 56 years. Finally, 29 respondents, also amounting to 6.5 percent, are aged 57 and above. In Table 2, it can be observed that 351 respondents, constituting 78.2 percent, identify as Christians. Additionally,

Table 3: Educational Qualification Distribution

Qualification	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
SSCE	128	28.5	28.5	28.5
OND/NCE	196	43.7	43.7	72.2
HND/BSC	79	17.6	17.6	89.8
MSC	9	2.0	2.0	91.8
Others	37	8.2	8.2	100.0
Total	449	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2016

Table 4: Local of Resident Distribution

Local Government	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
AKOKO EDO	103	22.9	22.9	22.9
ETSAKO CENTRAL	61	13.6	13.6	36.5
ETSAKO EAST	69	15.4	15.4	51.9
ETSAKO WEST	85	18.9	18.9	70.8
OWAN EAST	65	14.5	14.5	85.3
OWAN WEST	66	14.7	14.7	100.0
Total	449	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2016

Table 5: Sources of Awareness

Source	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
FRIEND	102	22.7	22.7	22.7
NEWSPAPER	85	18.9	18.9	41.6
TV	151	33.6	33.6	75.3
INTERNET	79	17.6	17.6	92.9
OTHERS	32	7.1	7.1	100.0
Total	449	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2016

80 respondents, making up 17.8 percent, adhere to the Islamic faith. Furthermore, 18 respondents, accounting for 4 percent, belong to other religions. Regarding respondents' highest educational qualification, table 3 shows that, 128 respondents, equivalent to 28.5 percent, possess SSCE qualifications. Furthermore, 198 respondents, constituting 43.7 percent, hold OND/NCE certificates. Additionally, 79 respondents, making up 17.6 percent, have HND/BSC qualifications. Moreover, 9 respondents, accounting for 2.0 percent, possess MSC degrees, while 37 respondents, totaling 8.2 percent, possess other qualifications. Table 4 presents data based on resident local government of residence. It is observed that 103 respondents, comprising 22.9 percent, reside in Akoko-Edo local government. Similarly, 61 respondents, representing 13.6 percent, reside in Etsako-central local government. Additionally, 69 respondents, accounting for 15.4 percent, are residents of Etsako-East local government. Moreover, 85 respondents, making up 18.9 percent, reside in Etsako-West local government. Furthermore, 65 respondents, constituting 14.5 percent, are residents of Owan-East local government, while 66 respondents, totaling 14.7 percent, are residents of Owan-West local government. Table 5 shows us the awareness sources of respondents. 102 respondents, comprising 22.7 percent, reported their awareness through a FRIEND. Similarly, 85 respondents, representing 18.9 percent, cited their awareness through NEWSPAPER. Additionally, 151 respondents, accounting for 33.6 percent, indicated their awareness through TV. Moreover, 79 respondents, making up 17.6 percent, mentioned their awareness through INTERNET. Furthermore, 32 respondents, totaling 7.1 percent, indicated their awareness through OTHER sources of information⁷.

4.2 Analysis

Table 6: Testing Hypothesis 1

	Value	Df	Asymp Sig (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	34.068 ^a	4	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	25.655	4	0.000
Linear-by-linear Asso	13.16	1	0.000
N of Valid Cases	449		

a. 4 cells (44.4%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 0.44
Results obtained from SPSS 20.0

Table 7: Testing Hypothesis 2

	Value	Df	Asymp Sig (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	9.236 ^a	2	0.010
Likelihood Ratio	9.582	2	0.008
Linear-by-linear Asso	0.297	1	0.586
N of Valid Cases	449		

a. 0 cells (0.00%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.34
Results obtained from SPSS 20.0

From Table 6 above, we tested our first hypothesis⁸. Since the calculated Chi-square (34.068) is greater than the tabulated value (9.488) at a 5% level of significance, we accept H_1 and infer that

⁷see appendix for questionnaire

⁸The hypothesis here states that Lassa fever awareness is independent of Religion

Table 8: Testing Hypothesis 3

	Value	Df	Asymp Sig (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	20.842 ^a	10	0.022
Likelihood Ratio	23.197	10	0.010
Linear-by-linear Asso	0.043	1	0.836
N of Valid Cases	449		

a. 10 cells (55.6%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.49
Results obtained from SPSS 20.0

Table 9: Testing Hypothesis 4

	Value	Df	Asymp Sig (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	34.491 ^a	6	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	15.323	6	0.018
Linear-by-linear Asso	1.000	1	0.317
N of Valid Cases	449		

a. 8 cells (66.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 0.05
Results obtained from SPSS 20.0

Lassa fever awareness is dependent on religion. In Table 7, we accepted the alternative hypothesis and inferred that Lassa fever awareness is dependent on gender since the calculated Chi-square (9.236) is greater than the tabulated value (5.991) at a 5% level of significance. Hypothesis 3 stated that Lassa fever awareness is independent of the local government of residents. The calculated value (20.842) is greater than the tabulated value (18.307) at a 5% level of significance, and we proceed to accept H_1 , concluding that Lassa fever awareness is dependent on the local government of residents. Finally from Table 8, we also infer that attitudinal behavior is dependent on awareness of Lassa fever.

4.3 Discussion

This study is a unique contribution to the literature on Lassa fever in Nigeria, with a specific emphasis on Edo North. The study's findings indicate that Lassa fever awareness is dependent on Religion, Gender, and Local Government of Residence and that Attitudinal behavior is dependent on the awareness of Lassa Fever. This result may be attributed to the region's good infrastructure, education, and communication facilities, which provide access to electronic and mass media through which information about Lassa fever in Nigeria is disseminated. Therefore, it is evident that with basic literacy and infrastructural development, the residents of the Senatorial district are sufficiently aware of Lassa fever. This awareness exists even without advanced knowledge of Health Science or investment in public awareness campaigns by the government.

Regarding the role of gender in creating awareness among the residents of Edo North Senatorial district towards Lassa fever, the findings of this study revealed that 52.4% of females and 47.6% of males are aware of Lassa fever. The female respondents exhibited a higher level of awareness about Lassa fever. This higher level of awareness among females might be attributed to their regular access to the internet, peer group interaction, watching television, and visiting health centers for various health-related issues, during which topics related to Lassa fever may arise.

5 Summary, Conclusion, and Recommendation

5.1 Summary

The research study on Lassa Fever awareness and attitudinal behavior in Edo North Senatorial District explores the relationship between awareness of Lassa Fever and behavioral attitudes. The study found that Lassa Fever awareness is dependent on factors such as religion, gender, and local government of residence. Females exhibited higher awareness levels, possibly due to factors like internet access and health center visits. The study used primary data collected through questionnaires from 500 respondents across six local government areas. Analysis was done using Chi-square tests in SPSS 20.0, showing significant relationships between Lassa Fever awareness and religion, gender, and local government of residence. The findings suggest the importance of basic literacy and infrastructure in raising awareness about Lassa Fever, even without extensive health science knowledge or government campaigns. The study provides valuable insights for policymakers and organizations aiming to address Lassa Fever misconceptions and improve public health awareness.

5.2 Conclusion

In conclusion, this study, the first of its kind in Nigeria, with a specific emphasis on Edo North, has revealed significant findings revealing Lassa Fever awareness and attitudinal behavior in Edo North Senatorial District. This indicates that awareness of Lassa Fever is influenced by various factors such as religion, gender, and local government of residence. The study highlights the importance of basic literacy and infrastructure in increasing awareness about Lassa Fever among the populace. The findings suggest that females tend to have higher awareness levels, possibly due to factors like internet access and health center visits. The study emphasizes the need for educational initiatives by governmental bodies and non-governmental organizations to combat misconceptions about Lassa Fever and improve public health awareness in Nigeria.

5.3 Recommendation

It is recommended that all three tiers of government and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) in Nigeria should intensify efforts to educate the populace through enlightenment campaigns, especially leveraging mass media and religious groups. These campaigns should focus on educating the public about the modes of transmission of the disease, its dangers, signs, and symptoms. Community participation in health education and environmental sanitation should be encouraged, with the involvement of traditional leaders, village heads, churches, mosques, and other NGOs. This collaborative effort will ensure active enlightenment against the practice of leaving food items in places accessible to rats, thus preventing the spread of the Lassa virus.

Furthermore, it is advised to refrain from using cats to control rats, as they may become a nuisance due to their droppings and urine. Household food items such as grains, garri, and yam powders should not be stored in cartons or bags but in sealed plastic or rodent-proof containers. Refuse and dustbins should be equipped with lids to deter rodents, and all rat hideouts should be blocked. Moreover, individuals should avoid spreading food where rats can access it and should clean the tops of canned juices before consumption or preferably use a straw.

Finally, we suggest that the Nigerian government, in collaboration with international organizations, should take a proactive approach to developing robust health databases and allocate resources to support researchers in conducting in-depth, long-term health research studies.

Appendix

Dear Respondent,

We, Peter Ohimai & Godwin Aipoh, are students of Auchi Polytechnic (aka Federal Polytechnic Auchi) in the Statistics Department are Investigating Lassa Fever Awareness and its Impact on Attitudinal Behavior Among Edo State Residents: A Case Study of the Edo North Senatorial District. This questionnaire is meant to solicit information on the ongoing study so that inference can be drawn. Your answer will be treated UTMOST SECRECY and shall not be revealed to a third party. THANK YOU

INSTRUCTION: PLS TICK [] WHERE YOU FEEL IS APPROPRIATE TO YOU

SECTION A: BIO-DATA INFORMATION

1. What is your age bracket? 17-24[], 25-32 [], 33-40 [], 41-48 [], 49-56 [], 57+ []
2. What is your sex? Male [], Female []
3. What is your religion? Christianity [], Muslim [], Others []
4. Your occupation? Student [], Trader [], Private Biz [], Civil servant [], Farmers [], Others []
5. What is your marital status? Single [], Married [], Divorced [], Separated [], Others []
6. What is your qualification? SSCE [], OND/NCE [], HND/BSC [], MSc [], Others []
7. Local Govt of residence: Akoko Edo [], Etsako Central [], Etsako West [], Etsako East [], Owan East [], Owan West []

SECTION B: LASSA FEVER ISSUE

8. Are you aware of Lassa fever? Yes [], No [], Maybe []
9. Indicate your source of awareness: Friend [], Family [], TV [], Internet [], Others []
10. If your spouse is infected with Lassa fever, will you continue? Yes [], No [], Maybe []
11. Does Lassa fever affect your eating habits? Yes [], No [], Maybe []
12. Did you take any traditional method to prevent Lassa fever? Yes [], No [], Maybe []
13. Will you visit the health facility for information on Lassa fever? Yes [], No [], Maybe []
14. Are you aware of any government intervention on Lassa fever? Yes [], No [], Maybe []
15. Do you think Lassa fever is fabricated or a hoax? Yes [], No [], Maybe []

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